

Shriya Kalyan

Professor Siddiqui

RHET 1302

12 December 2024

The access to quantum computing will widen the gap between developed and developing countries.

As quantum computing develops from being a simple theoretical construct, to an applied technology, it holds a potential promise for enhancements over everything from under healthcare and financial economics to environmental studies and cybersecurity. Capable of performing complex computations much faster than anything seen on a classical system, quantum technologies are a breakthrough in science due to the sheer power of innovation. However, huge costs and the special expertise required to develop and deploy quantum systems set up barriers for many countries, especially those in the developing world. This creates an inequality of access, known as the "quantum divide," where wealthy countries use and take advantage of quantum computing at the expense of the poorer ones (Mhlambululi and Makhamisa; Mishra). The result is that their capabilities of exploring quantum computing and even their possible participation in future technological progress get constrained. The quantum divide, thus, becomes a self-reinforcing cycle: technologically advanced nations increasingly build their technological lead, while the developing world remains at a place of marginalization.

The way quantum computing works is by leveraging the principles of quantum mechanics to solve problems way beyond what's possible on a normal everyday computer. While classic systems operate in binary states of 0 and 1, quantum computers use a qubit—the quantum bit—which can be in several states at once. This gives the quantum system another property, known as superposition, which enables it to perform some operations much

faster than previously estimated as it can compute multiple possibilities simultaneously (Fevrier 13220). Patel posits that quantum computing is already poised to change the medicine, finance, and shipping industries by optimizing processes and modeling (5). Its advanced computing power turns the technology into an economic force, acting as a foundation for discoveries that will drive innovation (Patel 8).

The economic potential of quantum computing is presently accessible only to wealthy nations, which already possess the significant technological industries. It is, therefore, realized that quantum technology and IoT may prove instrumental in the transition to the circular economy, where it could help organizations make real-time data analysis-based decisions on resource efficiency, product life cycle management, and waste reduction (Aljaafari and Alotaibi 1). In contrast, developing countries face enormous barriers, from research and development to infrastructure, putting them at a disadvantage (Lindsay 7). For example, the scarcity of money prevents them from investing in advanced research equipment and maintaining qualified scientists. Moreover, the countries also lack high-level computational infrastructure to carry out essential experiments using quantum labs, cryogenic setups, and efficient data centers. Even the few instances where they do make breakthroughs in research are further compromised by a lack of intellectual property protection and limited openness to international collaboration. These are just some of the structural challenges that make promising innovations in developing countries not only underfunded and underdeveloped but also usually unrecognized internationally. Lindsay also gives reason to be ready for post-quantum cryptography, which is of critical importance for countries with limited resources that face possible cybersecurity threats (2). Wealthy countries are investing intensively in leading positions in quantum computing, while poor countries cannot afford such expensive technology. Without international collaboration or policies in place, the disparities between these countries will only widen (Hong et al.).

It is also likely that the quantum technology in question will affect the extent of this weakness. There are some indications that short-cycle technologies, represented by quantum communication and sensing, are within the reach of resource-poor countries, while long-cycle technologies, epitomized by quantum computing, require much more fundamental research and heavy infrastructure investment (Kang et al. 254). Such a focus on short-cycle applications could facilitate the involvement of some developing countries in quantum development, but it also risks bypassing them in vital developments concerning quantum computing. To distribute the benefits of quantum computing evenly, global research partnerships and shared funding efforts should be formed to address these economic, educational, and policy challenges.

Millions of dollars are being invested in this field by the wealthy countries like the US and China through a combination of public money and investing in private businesses (Swayne). The way China approached this has been exemplary in how they spread the research activities in different quantum areas (e.g., quantum communication, quantum sensing), upheld by close coordination among academic institutions, government agencies, and private companies. By comparison, smaller countries, such as South Korea, due to limited resources, have no choice but to be more discrete in targeting their research activities to maximize their output (Kang et al. 248). At the same time, developing countries are unable to afford the initial investment for necessary infrastructure, placing them at risk of permanent disadvantage in this key area of technological development. Overcoming such disparities necessitates the active intervention of a government with policy interventions and collaboration. Mishra also highlights that subsidized, cloud-based quantum computing resources could be a public good that helps reduce such disparities. In the absence of such efforts, many nations risk being permanently marginalized in the global quantum era.

Another big area where the divides are seen is the development of skilled quantum human resources. The more economically developed countries are investing in education and training programs to create a large pool of talent to lead this sector. For example, universities in the United States, China, and Europe have established specific quantum curricula and courses on the high demand for labor (Greinert et al.). However, most developing countries do not have the academic infrastructure, finance, and infrastructure to support such programs. The growing quantum sector might drive a wedge between the skill sets and make it impossible for these countries to even interact with or use new technologies. Compounding the problem is the serious phenomenon of brain drain, which occurs when developing nations succeed in developing only a handful of well-trained professionals, only to see those individuals leave to seek opportunities and better pay in wealthier countries (Liman and Weber). Greinert et al. stress the need for international collaborations and funding schemes in place that enable both the training and retention of trained people in the Global South (referring to lower-income countries) so that a system exists whereby the trained professionals will help create the quantum ecosystem within the country of origin. Without doing so, developing nations will hardly ever build up a quantum workforce able to hold against global competition.

The dawn of quantum computing is bound to enhance the current global economic setup. For example, the impact of quantum computing on industrial competitiveness is immense; early adopters are accorded with major advantages in industries such as finance, healthcare, and manufacturing (Patel 5). Developed nations will be best positioned to exploit these privileges, from superior pharmaceutical development methodologies to state-of-the-art AI-enriched economic systems. Sood and Pooja underline the fact that there are trillion-dollar prospects in quantum technology, with the countries that could exploit it well benefitting

from the advantages that are accruing (7). The possibility of reinforcement with exponential growth means a prevailing position for the developed economies.

On the other hand, the countries that are underdeveloped risk exclusion from this technological evolution entirely. As Mishra mentions, quantum computing may deepen the gaps in many fields related to health and education. For example, wealthy states could use quantum algorithms to change the history of personalized medicine, while resource-constrained countries fail on basic infrastructure challenges. Equally, quantum optimization might be utilized in advanced economies by financial institutions to further cement their lead in world trade, hence making catching up even more impossible. Hong et al. argue that global alliances are necessary so as not to widen such inequities.

Equitable access to quantum computing requires more than overcoming a technical barrier; it is equally a moral one. By using the Quantum Technology for Development (QT4D) framework through science diplomacy, Mhlambululi and Makhamsa argue that this helps bridge the gulf in technology between the Global North and South. Again, the approach underlines co-governance, sharing knowledge, and capacity-building measures in distributing benefits emanating from quantum technology. Each quantum investment should match up with broader Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including efforts to reduce inequalities, improve health, and better education (Hong et al.). Concretely, that would be quantum workforce development grants and resource-sharing partnerships. The developing world will also have to start working on the implementation of post-quantum cryptography standards to help prepare for a future of vulnerabilities in cybersecurity. That is, increasing low-resource countries' capacities needs to be a multidimensional effort with an emphasis on experiential education, raising public awareness, and investing in building a local quantum innovation ecosystem (Greinert et al.). Activities at the international policy level should be complemented by promoting equitable access to quantum technology.

While quantum computing can revolutionize industries and reshape the global economy, prohibitive costs and technical capabilities even threaten to make it further increase the gap between developed and developing nations. International cooperation should be the number one priority, with the help of the well-developed countries sharing their natural resources, technologies, as well as the infrastructure to foster the developing nations. It is of utmost importance to allocate financial resources to the fields of quantum education, workforce training, and creating policies that promote equitable access to technology to close the gap. The global partnerships can also turn out to be the medium for realizing the ethical innovations so that technological advancements are perceived as constructive for humanity. Through frameworks like The Quantum Technology for Development and the practice of shared responsibility, the countries can come up with a structure that ensures that the benefits of quantum computing are available to all. A synchronous attempt to democratize quantum technology is a desirable scenario that will help mankind in achieving world unity instead of creating division.

Works Cited

- Aljaafari, M., and S. Alotaibi. "Importance of Quantum Technology in Economy Paradigm Shift." *Soft Computing*, 2023, pp. 1-15, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-023-08514-0>.
- Greinert, F., M. S. Ubben, I. N. Dogan, et al. "Advancing Quantum Technology Workforce: Industry Insights into Qualification and Training Needs." *EPJ Quantum Technology*, vol. 11, 2024, article 82, <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjqt/s40507-024-00294-2>.
- Hong, Xianna, et al. "The Impact of Digitalization on the Rich and the Poor: Digital Divide or Digital Inclusion?" *Technology in Society*, vol. 78, 2024, article 102634, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2024.102634>.
- Kang, Inje, et al. "Divergence of Knowledge Production Strategies for Emerging Technologies between Late Industrialized Countries: Focusing on Quantum Technology." *ETRI Journal*, vol. 42, no. 1, 2020, pp. 246-259, <https://doi.org/10.4218/etrij.2019-0501>.
- Liman, Anders, and Kate Weber. "Quantum Computing: Bridging the National Security–Digital Sovereignty Divide." *European Journal of Risk Regulation*, vol. 14, no. 3, 2023, pp. 476–483, www.cambridge.org/core/journals/european-journal-of-risk-regulation/article/quantum-computing-bridging-the-national-securitydigital-sovereignty-divide/515B8E8F0645CC5A6A7ADBC25AEF8C90.
- Lindsay, Jon R. "Surviving the Quantum Cryptocalypse." *Strategic Studies Quarterly*, vol. 14, no. 2, 2020, pp. 49–73. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/26915277.
- Mhlambululi, Mafu, and Senekane Makhamisa. "Quantum Technology for Development Framework as a Tool for Science Diplomacy." *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics*, vol. 8, 2023, article 1279376, <https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2023.1279376>.
- Mishra, Abhilash. *Quantum Futures: International Development and the Quantum Computing Transition*. USAID, 2023.

Patel, Hiral B. "The Future of Quantum Computing and Its Potential Applications."

ResearchGate, vol. 23, no. 11, 2023.

Sood, S. K., and Pooja. "Quantum Computing Review: A Decade of Research." *IEEE*

Transactions on Engineering Management, vol. 71, 2024, pp. 6662–76,

doi:10.1109/TEM.2023.3284689.

Swayne, Matt. "Congressional Budget Office Reviews \$1.8 Billion, 5-Year National

Quantum Initiative Reauthorization Act." *The Quantum Insider*, 2 Nov. 2024,

<https://thequantuminsider.com/2024/11/02/congressional-budget-office-reviews-1-8-billion-5-year-national-quantum-initiative-reauthorization-act/>.

Valdez, Fevrier, and Patricia Melin. "A Review on Quantum Computing and Deep Learning

Algorithms and Their Applications." *Soft Computing*, vol. 18, 2023, pp. 13217–36,

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-022-07037-4>.